

The Comprehensive Application of Ecological Techniques for Carbon Sequestration in Farmland Soils

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Suggested Citation

Chen, S., & Fang, P. (2024). The Comprehensive Application of Ecological Techniques for Carbon Sequestration in Farmland Soils. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(5), 728-737.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(5\).65](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(5).65)

Abstract:

Human activities, such as the combustion of fossil fuels and alteration in land use, have resulted in a significant and persistent increase in atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentrations. Among these activities, greenhouse gas emissions from agricultural soils represent a critical contributor to this trend. To mitigate the effects of accelerating climate change and enhance soil quality, there is an urgent need to increase the organic matter content in agricultural soil systems. This review examines the mechanisms of soil carbon sequestration within agriculture and evaluates key

strategies employed in agricultural ecological engineering for carbon capture. Specific methods discussed include conservation tillage, exogenous carbon addition, and the use of earthworms. For each method, we detail the underlying mechanisms, as well as their respective advantages and limitations. The objective of this review is to provide a comprehensive theoretical framework and practical recommendations for improving agricultural practices aimed at enhancing soil carbon sequestration.

Keywords: *Soil carbon sequestration, soil organic carbon, farmland, ecological management practices.*

Introduction

Since 1750, human activities, such as the combustion of fossil fuels and alterations in land use, have led to a significant rise in atmospheric CO₂ levels, increasing from approximately 280 to 385 ppmv, well above pre-industrial values (Al & Paasche, 2007). In the pre-industrial era, land ecosystems are estimated to have emitted about 320 Pg of carbon into the atmosphere (Lal, 2004a). China, one of the world's largest agricultural countries, had a crop production of 62.144 million tons and a sown area of 11.33405 million hectares in 2015. It is urgent to stabilize and reduce greenhouse gas (GHG)

concentrations in the atmosphere to mitigate human impacts on the climate system.

The soil organic carbon (SOC) reservoir constitutes roughly two-thirds of the total organic carbon found on land and is approximately twice the size of the atmospheric carbon pool, making it a critical component (Lal, 2004b). The IPCC's Fifth Assessment Report identifies agriculture as having the greatest potential for greenhouse gas reduction in the economic sector up to 2030, primarily through SOC sequestration. Agricultural soil carbon sequestration is considered a key method for mitigating GHG emissions and global climate change, with a potential mitigation capacity of

approximately 8 Pg CO₂-eq per year. Improvements in crop and livestock management and promoting carbon sequestration in agricultural processes—including soil carbon management in croplands and grasslands, agroforestry, and biochar—could reduce emissions by 1.8-4.1 Gt CO₂-eq per year.

Agricultural soils account for 14% of total greenhouse gas emissions (Pachauri et al., 2015), emphasizing the growing need to boost soil organic matter to tackle climate change and enhance soil quality. Studies show that for degraded farmland soils, each additional ton of soil carbon has the potential to boost wheat yields by 20 to 40 kg per hectare, corn by 10 to 20 kg per hectare, and cowpea ranging from 0.5 to 1 kg per hectare. Carbon sequestration not only enhances food security but also has the capacity to extract 0.4 to 1.2 gigatons of CO₂ annually from fossil fuel emissions, equating to 5% to 15% of global fossil fuel emissions. Compared to natural ecosystems like forests and grasslands, cropland ecosystems are particularly vulnerable to human activities. During harvest, the above-ground parts of crops are either returned to the field or left to decompose, with most of the carbon rapidly being released back into the atmosphere as CO₂. Thus, the net contribution of cropland ecosystems to atmospheric CO₂ depends on changes in their soil carbon pools. Enhancing soil carbon sequestration in agricultural lands not only revitalizes degraded soils, boosting fertility and increases crop yields (Lal, 2004a), but also provides a cost-effective and efficient way for reducing CO₂ emissions, offering medium- to long-term advantages (Antle et al., 2002).

Agricultural Ecological Management Practices

Common ecological practices for improving soil carbon sequestration in agricultural fields encompass no-till farming, the use of crop residue cover, planting cover crops, rotating crops, and implementing integrated nutrient management. These practices mainly facilitate carbon sequestration by enhancing soil

biodiversity, boosting microbial activity, and enhancing the soil's physical and chemical characteristics. Research has increasingly focused on bolstering the capacity of protected soil carbon sinks through ecological land management. Studies have proved that ecological land management practices positively influence SOC content. These ecological management practices not only boost carbon sequestration but also enhance soil quality, increase moisture retention, and support the sustainability of agricultural ecosystems.

Agricultural management practices have affected the SOC retention within China's topsoil (Gen, 2003; Pan et al., 2004; Wu et al., 2010). Reduced tillage is widely recognized for leading to layered distribution of different soil properties, such as SOC (Brye et al., 2007; Franzluebbers, 2002), soil structure (Mrabet, 2002), microbial organic matter (Melero et al., 2009), and enzyme activity (Sá & Lal, 2009). Numerous studies have demonstrated that tillage methods significantly affect microbial biomass (Sun, Jia, Zhang, McLaughlin, Liang, et al., 2016), community composition (Jia et al., 2016), and metabolic activity (Sun, Jia, Zhang, McLaughlin, Zhang, et al., 2016). No-till farming greatly decreases soil carbon loss by reducing the disruption of soil aggregates and limiting the exposure of fresh and unstable organic matter to microbial breakdown. No-till farming is considered an effective and eco-friendly approach for soil carbon sequestration (Lal, 2004a) and, along with increased crop residue management, which enhances carbon input, no-till represents two important and widely recognized strategies for improving carbon storage (Kern & Johnson, 1993). However, only 5% of global farmland (1379 Mha) practices no-till (Lal, 2004a). Combining no-till with increased crop residue strategies, which involve both increasing SOC inputs and reducing SOC decomposition, constitutes the most effective C sequestration measures. Despite its significant carbon sequestration potential, the average rate of carbon sequestration in no-till systems is limited by low carbon input, particularly in the northwest region of China, where crop net primary productivity (NPP) is typically low (Yan

et al., 2007). Although a large quantity of crop straw is produced globally, only 50-60% is returned to the soil (Lal, 1999), and in China, approximately only 25% is returned (X. Wang et al., 2010).

Cover crops are plants that fill soil gaps either during the main crop's growing season or after its harvest, both temporally and spatially. Due to their strong root penetration and high biomass, cover crops can enable the development of soil aggregate structures and improve SOC and overall soil quality through their root growth. Meta-analyses indicate that planting cover crops can substantially boost SOC content, with an overall increase of up to 15.5% (Jian et al., 2020). Compared to monoculture of cover crops, mixed planting is more effective in enhancing SOC content, with leguminous cover crops showing the best carbon sequestration effects (Topps et al., 2021). However, some studies suggest that planting cover crops does not always result in higher SOC content, and in some cases, SOC levels may decrease in the 0-50 cm soil layer following the introduction of cover crops (Camarotto et al., 2020). These varying results may be attributed to variations in soil properties and the duration of cover crop cultivation. SOC components tend to be more responsive to different types of cover crops compared to the total SOC (Bukovsky-Reyes et al., 2019).

Incorporating crop straw into the soil can effectively modify SOC components, increasing the relative content of O-alkyl C, carbonyl C, and alkyl C, as well as the A/O-A ratio and aromaticity (Miao et al., 2019). After straw incorporation, there are two decomposition pathways: one involves microbial humification, where organic matter is transformed into humic substances and retained in the soil; the other involves heterotrophic microbial decomposition, which releases CO₂ into the atmosphere, observable as soil respiration. Both processes are linked to soil microbial properties. Straw incorporating into the soil leads to the breakdown of various organic materials, such as polysaccharides, proteins, and lignin, which contributes to the formation of large soil aggregates (Tripathi et al., 2014). Research found

that different types of straw, due to variations in cellulose, lignin, nitrogen, and C/N ratios exhibit differences in biodegradability, ultimately resulting in variations in soil respiration intensity and SOC levels (Cao et al., 2016). Straw incorporation significantly stimulates soil microbial activity, increasing microbial biomass and boosting the activity of β -glycosidase and dehydrogenase, with dehydrogenase showing the strongest correlation with soil respiration.

Biochar is an innovative, carbon-rich substance recognized for its porous structure, large surface area, and exceptional adsorption properties, and stability (El-Naggar et al., 2019; Gaskin et al., 2008). Applying biochar can boost the formation of soil aggregates and enhance the soil's ability to retain nutrients and water (Li et al., 2019; Li et al., 2019; Mi et al., 2015), enhance soil porosity and fungal populations, as well as improve soil pH and water retention capacity (Lehmann et al., 2008; Rodionov et al., 2010; Schmidt et al., 2001). Additionally, biochar promotes crop growth and increases the effectiveness of nutrient uptake and use (Xu et al., 2021; Cui et al., 2020; Gao et al., 2020). Since biochar is produced under high-temperature conditions, it is an inert solid material with highly carboxylated and stable aromatic structures, making it less susceptible to microbial decomposition compared to straw (Ke et al., 2014). However, like straw, biochar can serve as a binding medium to enhance soil aggregate formation and interact with other organic materials and minerals in the soil to further promote aggregation. The increase in organic carbon content within large soil aggregates helps maintain the long-term stability of micro-aggregates that contribute to aggregate formation. Research has demonstrated that applying biochar increases the soil's total carbon storage capacity more effectively than straw incorporation, with newly added exogenous organic carbon primarily distributed in large aggregates (Qiao et al., 2018). Compared to micro-aggregates (< 0.25 mm), biochar is more likely to associate with large soil aggregates. Biochar application typically surpasses straw incorporation in boosting the organic carbon levels in soil aggregates. Within the top 0-20 cm

of the soil layer, combining biochar with nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium notably increases the organic carbon contribution of large soil aggregates, while decreasing that of micro-aggregates (Gao et al., 2020).

However, biochar has a higher pH and relatively lower nutrient bioavailability, which can negatively affect soil fertility, nutrient activity and utilization, and crop growth (Dong et al., 2022). A research involving a four-year continuous monitoring revealed that applying biochar consistently lowers methane (CH₄) emissions from rice paddies, with annual reductions ranging from 20% to 51% (Liu et al., 2014; C. Wang et al., 2018). In contrast to direct straw incorporation, which significantly increases CH₄ emissions, converting straw into straw-based biochar and then applying it can substantially reduce CH₄ emissions from rice paddies (Shen et al., 2014). Simulations using the Water-Nitrogen Management Model (WNMM) suggest that the primary factor contributing to the reduced CH₄ emissions from rice paddies is the increased soil redox potential (Eh) associated with biochar application. The simulations suggest that biochar application increases soil Eh by 30–40 mV, with a good correlation between simulated CH₄ emissions and observed values ($R^2 > 0.73$). The decrease in the abundance of methanogens and the ratio of methanogen abundance to methanotroph abundance in rice paddy soils resulting from biochar application, is a significant factor in the reduced CH₄ emissions.

Earthworms influence soil and humus dynamics through their ingestion, excretion, secretion, and burrowing activities, which alter soil porosity, physical properties, and hydraulic characteristics. Earthworms can be categorized based on their soil distribution into endogeic and epigeic species. Endogeic earthworms primarily consume soil organic matter, while epigeic earthworms feed on plant residues and soil organic matter. Both types of earthworms may contribute to integrating carbon from various sources into soil aggregates. Earthworms can form organic micro-aggregates in their gut, with epigeic earthworms incorporating new organic material from litter into various soil carbon

pools and aggregates, while existing soil organic matter is incorporated into larger aggregates by endogeic species (Sánchez-de León et al., 2014).

The organic-inorganic aggregates excreted by earthworms can enhance soil aggregation (Blanchart et al., 1990), structural integrity (Vleeschauwer & Lal, 1981), and resistance to tension (McKenzie & Dexter, 1987), thus affecting soil organic matter mineralization, which is influenced by soil type and moisture (McInerney & Bolger, 2000). Earthworm casts contain growth hormones such as indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) (Li et al., 2002), which can increase soil enzyme activity, including urease and sucrose synthase, thereby boosting microbial activity is influenced by rhizodeposition, which serves as a key energy source in the soil food web and plays a vital role in soil carbon sequestration. Earthworms enhance rhizodeposition by promoting plant growth and root carbon input, converting unstable root-derived carbon into more resistant forms (Wu et al., 2017). Research has demonstrated that earthworm activity leads to carbon loss under different types of litter (clover, maize straw, wheat straw, sheep manure, and sugarcane bagasse fibers), primarily because of its impact on soil fungal and bacterial abundance, with a smaller correlation to carbon-degrading enzyme activity. The chemical composition of litter influences the impact of earthworms on soil carbon. Earthworms tend to decrease particulate organic carbon (POC) and soil organic carbon (SOC) when interacting with high-solubility litter species, but show no significant effect with high-lignin litter species. Additionally, incorporating sewage sludge into earthworm casts enhances soil biological activity and microbial growth, with sewage sludge enhancing soil microbial biomass by 8-28% (Dar, 1996; Marinari et al., 2000). Earthworms significantly increase the C to N enzyme activity ratio in low-lignin litter species, such as clover, maize straw, and wheat straw, have this effect. However, the impact is reversed with high-lignin litter species, such as sheep manure and sugarcane bagasse fibers (Zheng et al., 2018).

Combining earthworms with straw-derived carbon to amend rice paddy soils can address

carbon deficits in depleted soils (Aira & Domínguez, 2008; John et al., 2015). Research found that a density of about 500-600 earthworms per square meter is ideal for carbon sequestration and the reintegration of nutrients from crop residues, with higher densities potentially leading to competition for resources or stress among earthworms. Soil moisture and type are key factors regulating earthworm-induced microbial activity (John et al., 2015). Earthworms can transport significant amounts transferring carbon from the soil surface to deeper layers, effectively mixing the soil and markedly increasing humification and overall decomposition rates. This process influences soil carbon sequestration by balancing the breakdown and stabilization of litter carbon (Lubbers et al., 2017; Zhu et al., 2016). Studies suggest that earthworm addition accelerates soil litter decomposition by affecting microbial community composition, structure, and activity, thus speeding up the turnover of SOC (Binet et al., 1998; Jiang et al., 2011).

However, further research is needed to fully understand earthworm effects on soil carbon dynamics, especially in non-invaded soils. Some studies indicated that introducing non-native earthworms can lead to soil carbon loss (Alban & Berry, 1994), while others reported contrary results (Wironen & Moore, 2006). Future efforts to forecast or model the effects of rising atmospheric CO₂ concentrations on soil carbon dynamics across various ecosystems should take into account the presence and feeding behavior of earthworms (Sánchez-de León et al., 2014). Earthworm mucus, composed of proteins, peptides, and carbohydrates, is an unstable carbon source (Hoang et al., 2017). This complexity complicates the contribution of earthworms to soil carbon sequestration. Earthworm casts, having a lower pH and higher nutrient bioavailability than biochar, significantly enhance the soil's physical and chemical properties. They reduce soil density of soil, suppress soil moisture evaporation, mitigate soil degradation from prolonged inorganic fertilizer use, and improve crop quality.

Crop rotation is a globally practiced agricultural method that alters the sequence of crop planting,

enhancing plant diversity and creating residual effects in the soil. This practice affects the soil environment through physical changes and post-harvest residues, which are crucial for soil biodiversity and ecosystem functions (Zhang et al., 2021). Research indicated that crop rotation, particularly when combined with cover crops, can boost soil carbon and microbial biomass carbon by about 8.5% and 20.7%, respectively, emphasizing the role of underground communities in soil carbon enhancement. Key benefits of crop rotation include increased organic carbon input, which significantly affects soil properties and processes. It enhances soil structure, increases macro-porosity, boosts water infiltration, supports biomass growth, and promotes microbial diversity, providing multiple benefits to agricultural ecosystems (Lal, 2011).

Crop rotation encourages the development of larger soil aggregates and boosts their organic carbon content (Du et al., 2013). It has been shown to improve the stability of large soil aggregates (Fan et al., 2021). Diverse crop rotation systems, particularly those with varied functional traits, lead to larger carbon pools. Perennial crops and cover crops significantly impact ecosystem functions by increasing primary productivity, altering residue chemistry, and modifying soil community diversity. These changes improve carbon input quality and quantity while reducing leaching and erosion. To maximize soil carbon through crop rotation, strategies include increasing the functional diversity of cover crops and perennials, boosting carbon inputs—especially from roots—and extending perennial cover duration. Research indicated that rotations involving legumes or perennials are more effective in maintaining SOC, compared to high nitrogen fertilizer applications. Increasing crop rotation diversity and carbon inputs enhances SOC concentrations and ecosystem benefits (King & Blesh, 2018).

Conclusion

The primary ecological strategies for carbon sequestration in agricultural soils are utilizing paddy fields as carbon sinks, enhancing carbon sequestration and reduction through

fertilization, and repurposing agricultural waste to reduce carbon emissions. The methods for increasing soil carbon sequestration through different organic matter returns should be adapted to local conditions based on the specific implementation targets. Further research is needed on carbon sequestration methods for different soil properties and tillage types.

China has rich and diverse soil resources, with notable variations in soil properties due to various parent materials. Studying the impacts of different regional agricultural management practices and terrain, soil, and vegetation on the dominant microbial populations and their abundance in carbon sequestration is crucial. Molecular biology techniques and carbon stable isotope tracing methods can be used to quantitatively study the distribution and transformation of microbial assimilated carbon in the soil carbon pool. This research can offer technical assistance for effective scientific management of soil fertility and offer a scientific basis for accurately assessing the capacity of agricultural soils for carbon sequestration and the development of regional low-carbon agriculture strategies. For studies with inconsistent results and varying initial soil conditions, meta-analysis should be conducted to integrate findings and derive systematic conclusions.

Acknowledgement

Gratitude is extended to the Key Laboratory of Agro-Environment in the Midstream of the Yangtze Plain, Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Affairs, P.R. China, for their invaluable support in the completion of this research. Appreciation is also expressed to all individuals and organizations who contributed to this work, directly or indirectly.

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